

ON THE KETTEMANN CORPUS OF GERMAN SPEECH ERRORS

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Abstract

The Kettemann Corpus of German Speech Errors is shown in Nora Wiedenmann's Error-Type Categorization, here with English comments, together with statistical overviews of different error types of the speakers Bernhard Kettemann and Ilse Bernhard Kettemann listed according to affected linguistic units.

Keywords: speech errors, association, substitution, intrusion, insertion, omission, metathesis, reversal, fusion, blend, anticipation, repetition, perseveration, dissimilation, phonetics, phonology, vowel, consonant, morpheme, synonym, antonym.

1. Introductory remarks by Bernhard Kettemann

I am grateful to Dr. Nora Wiedenmann for making my German speech error data available online. She has categorized the errors and added illuminating comments. The corpus is much more useful now than it was before. And it is only due to her that it is available at all. Nora Wiedenmann contacted me in the early nineteen-nineties about my corpus of approx. 600 German speech errors after she had read my 1981 paper on the reality of phonetic features ("Evidence for the Reality of Segmental and Transsegmental Features". In: Dressler, Wolfgang U. / Pfeiffer, Oskar E. / Rennison, John R. (eds.), *Phonologica 1980. Akten der Vierten Internationalen Phonologie-Tagung*. Wien 29. Juni - 2. Juli 1980. Innsbruck: Institut für Sprachwissenschaft. p. 237-243.), where I mentioned my collection. I sent it to her, she worked on it and she included it in her groundbreaking 1998 "yellow book" in landscape format *Versprecher. Phänomene und Daten*, in which she analyzed and published her own corpus too and the two Meringer corpora. Unfortunately, the warehouse where the publisher (Edition Praesens in Vienna) had stored the books burnt down some years ago and Nora Wiedenmann is now reacting to changing technology and rising demand for access to authentic data with this new online edition.

Speech errors are important language data for a variety of reasons. They involve, for example, anticipations, perseverances, additions or deletions of linguistic units, such as distinctive features, phonemes, morphemes, syl-

lables, words and phrases, units that can thus be proved to be psychologically real and be used as evidence to show that the use of these linguistic units is rule governed. Speech errors thus provide a window on the mental processes underlying language production and provide data to decide between competing hypotheses, approaches, and theories. For linguists working empirically, speech errors therefore present an invaluable resource for their research.

Take “Schrip-“ instead of the planned “Schrittempo” (error 055 by IK). Here we have an anticipation of the labial gesture instead of the planned dental plosive, probably induced by the following planned labiality (+ and – nasal) of “mp” and lip rounding of “o”. This shows that phonetic features like nasality and labiality are psychologically real units in speech production.

The corpus was not conceived as aimed at special phenomena but as a continuous record of naturally occurring production data of specific speakers over a specific period of time.

2. Description of Main Speakers

2.1. Bernhard Kettemann (BK)

Dr. Bernhard Kettemann was born and raised in Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany, and finished his MA in English and German there. He has been living in Graz since 1975, where he is professor of English Linguistics at the Department of English Studies of the University of Graz. He collected his speech error data between 1979 and 1990 in two handwritten booklets. He recorded the errors he produced between the ages of 33 and 44.

Over the years, his pronunciation has adapted to the Graz city dialect, which is a variety of Southern Bavarian. He uses an apicoalveolar /r/. In his speech error data he almost always noted voicelessness clearly in his phonetic transcription. When recording his speech error data he noted the actually produced voiceless variants of the consonants, the plosives, and the fricatives in the rubric “error/instead of”. (It remains unclear, however, how far nasals and liquids have also been devoiced by the speakers in the Kettemann corpus because this was not marked consistently.)

2.2. Ilse Kettemann (IK)

Mag. Ilse Kettemann was born in Klagenfurt and raised in Klein St. Paul and Klagenfurt in Carinthia, Austria. She finished an MA in English and German at the University of Graz and has been living in Graz since 1974, where she is a lecturer in Business English at the School of Social Sciences at the University of Graz. Her speech errors were produced and recorded between the ages of 23 and 34.

The Klagenfurt dialect and the Graz dialect both belong to different varieties of Southern Bavarian. IK and BK both pronounce the final morpheme “-ig” with a voiceless dorsovelar plosive. (The same pronunciation can also be assumed for the three speakers of the Meringer corpora.)

IK uses a uvular /r/. Please note her frequent labialization processes which may affect coarticulatory changes in vowels and consonants due to baby talk phenomena when her two children were small, born 1983 and 1985. This effect can be seen from error 150 onwards.

2.3. Other Speakers

Other speakers have been identified by their first names, except in the case of TV or radio announcers.

3. The Data

The data are included in the appendices 1, 2, and 3 according to speakers in chronological order and in the appendices 4, 5, and 6 according to error types.

4. Comparative Statistics

I also include three statistical overviews of different error types of the speakers BK and IK listed according to affected linguistic units (vowels, consonants, and higher units).

4.1. Speech Errors of Morphemes, Words, Phrases, and Semantics

To compare with speaker data of other corpora s. Wiedenmann (1998: 25).

Speaker BK: 218 cases = 100%;

speaker IK: 249 cases = 100%

4.2. Speech Errors of Consonants

To compare with speaker data of other corpora s. Wiedenmann (1998: 28).

Speaker BK: 218 cases = 100%;

speaker IK: 249 cases = 100%

error type / unit

error type / unit

4.3. Speech Errors of Vowels, Speech Gestures, and Other Phenomena

To compare with speaker data of other corpora s. Wiedenmann (1998: 31).

Speaker BK: 218 cases = 100%;
 error type / unit

speaker IK: 249 cases = 100%
 error type / unit

4.4. Legend for the Corpus Data and for the Preceding Statistics

Abbreviations and Characters of Transcription etc.

Speaker BK: Bernhard Kettemann; tip-alveolar /r/;

Speaker IK: Ilse Kettemann; uvular /r/;

Matthias (*1983); Andrea (*1985): both uvular /r/;

concerning the other speakers of Kettemann's Error Corpus, the quality of /r/ is mentioned if relevant.

Remarks on dissimilation, resp. 'similation' in the left column of every line:

d: dissimilation

d-s: dissimilation and in the same error case also 'similation'

s: 'similation', the contrary of dissimilation

Error Type:

an: anticipation, substitutive or else additive

a+e: anticipation plus following elision / omission (i.e., the same as: shift) of the same just before inserted unit, resp. as substitutive case: A+e

ant: substitutive error concerning an antonym (word or phrase)

antkon: contamination from two (or in rare cases three) word or phrase units: in antonymous relation one to another; rare cases

assim: assimilation; no speech error

asz: an error to be explained by association (also caused by visual or auditive perception): substitutive or else contaminating, and this either for the complete unit or only a part of it

e: elision / omission of a unit

e+c: elision plus (system-inherent) "correction" using the same unit (i.e. a certain shift), inserting, resp. E+c: substitutive case of "correction"

e+i: dissimilating elision / omission; the i (for: intended unit) showing the position of at least one intended or uttered unit, thus: 'Backward Masking', resp. regressive (anticipatory) dissimilation

i+e: dissimilating elision / omission; the i (for: intended unit) showing the position of at least one intended or uttered unit, thus: 'Forward Masking', resp. progressive (repetitive) dissimilation

i+e+i: dissimilating elision / omission the i (for: intended unit) showing the position of at least one intended or uttered unit, before or after the omitted unit, thus: ambiguous according to masking, resp. dissimilation direction

kat: substitutive error concerning a semantic category (e.g. a word / concept field); other authors' term for this error type: "substitution"

katkon: contamination of at least two units concerning a semantic category (e.g. a word / concept field); blend / fusion; in two or (very rare) three parts

man: broken metathesis / exchange / permutation / reversal / transposition; at least perceivable the first part: the anticipation; a so-called incomplete metathesis

met: metathesis / exchange / permutation / reversal / transposition

re: repetition (similar to perseveration in pathology)

Rep: repetition from visual or auditive perception of the own speech (or of that of another speaker), or from visible actions

ret: speech with retardation, showing sometimes additional vowels between retarded consonants

?: error not categorizable (e.g., because of too few context)

3-1-2, or similar: serialization numbers of erred units (1-2-3: canonical serialization) as a certain complex serialization error

Error Unit:

gen: genus
ges: speech gesture
kas: Kasus; grammatical case
k: consonant, resp. consonant cluster
k,v: CV sequence; not absolutely the same as a syllable
kvk: CVC sequence; not absolutely the same as a syllable
m: morpheme
mod: Modus; grammatical mood
num: grammatical number
per: grammatical person
rule: grammatical rule
sth: stimmhaft; speech gesture for voiced
stl: stimmlos: speech gesture for voiceless
t: grammatical tense
v: vowel, resp. vowels (diphthongs)
v,k: VC sequence; syllable rhyme
w: word

Sounds (columns "spoken" / "instead of"), in IPA characters (among others):

ʔ: glottal stop; ŋ: dorsovelar nasal; ʃ: alveo-palatal fricative, voiceless;
ʒ: alveo-palatal fricative, voiced, as in French 'jargon';
ɔ: short -o- as in German 'ob'; ə: shwa as finally in German 'Rente'

Speech Gestures: lab: labial; alv: tip-alveolar; vel: velum; velar

Word Accent / Stress: accent before the first letter of a stressed unit

Column "corrected": 1 = yes; 0 = no; ? = unknown

5. Conclusion

The Kettemann Corpus of German Speech Errors is again shown in Nora Wiedenmann's Error-Type Categorization, here with English comments.

Appendices

The data are included in the appendices 1, 2, and 3 according to speakers in chronological order and in the appendices 4, 5, and 6 according to error types.

References

- Kettemann, Bernhard. 1980.** “On the reality of segmental and transsegmental features”. In *Folia Linguistica*, XIV/3-4, 437-452; 1981 as: “Evidence for the Reality of Segmental and Transsegmental Features”. In Dressler, Wolfgang U. / Pfeiffer, Oskar E. / Rennison, John R. (eds.), *Phonologica 1980. Akten der Vierten Internationalen Phonologietagung*. Wien 29. Juni - 2. Juli 1980 (pp. 237-243). Innsbruck: Institut für Sprachwissenschaft.
- Wiedenmann, Nora. 1998.** *Versprecher: Phänomene und Daten. Mit Materialien auf Diskette*. Wien: Wissenschaftsverlag Edition Praesens.